

Working Group Report: Review and Reconsideration of the IUCN Technical Guidelines on the Management of *Ex Situ* Populations for Conservation: Why, when (and how) to establish an *ex situ* population

Participants

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Background

Ex situ populations and activities best serve conservation if they are part of an overall conservation strategy for the species. However, species conservation strategies have not been developed for many threatened species, and many existing strategies do not formally evaluate the appropriateness of *ex situ* activities.

From the field perspective, conservation planners often struggle with how to evaluate if and when *ex situ* conservation measures should be considered for the species. Similarly, the *ex situ* community struggles with how to prioritize species for *ex situ* conservation, as well as how to decide the form that *ex situ* management should take. The lack of clear guidance and criteria in this evaluation process means that some *ex situ* activities may be inappropriate or ineffective in contributing to species conservation, and also that some species in urgent need of *ex situ* activities may escape our attention.

The *IUCN Technical Guidelines on the Management of Ex Situ Populations for Conservation* have the potential to guide both the *in situ* and *ex situ* communities in evaluating the appropriate role (if any) that *ex situ* management can play in the conservation of specific species. The current IUCN guidelines, developed in 2002, provide general guidance but have been suggested by some to be ambiguous enough to allow for contradictory interpretations. Additional expertise and analytical tools are now available that can support this process, suggesting that a revision of the IUCN guidelines would be timely and useful for deciding if and when individuals should be taken from the wild for the purpose of supporting species conservation.

Scope

This working group was convened to expand and adapt the *IUCN Technical Guidelines on the Management of Ex Situ Populations for Conservation* so that they give clear guidelines to all parties involved in the conservation of a species on how to decide IF *ex situ* activities should be included in the overall conservation activities for the species and WHAT FORM these activities should take. The revised guidelines should:

- Address the specific issue of taking individuals (both whole organisms and 'living tissues') from the wild;
- Be non-taxon specific and thus apply to all life forms;
- Apply to both situations where a taxon is not yet kept *ex situ* and to those where *ex situ* populations may already exist;
- Include all *ex situ* activities (including, but not restricted to, zoos, aquaria and botanical gardens); and
- Apply to both range-wide or regional/local initiatives.

The working group agreed to both the need for and scope of the suggested guidelines revision. Specific points that were made during this discussion included:

- Guidelines should be specific about subspecies, geographic variations, and widespread species.
- The impact on remaining populations in the wild must be considered.
- The guidelines should incorporate the potential benefits of management research using surrogate species.
- Managers are sometimes reluctant to bring in animals from the wild, even when this would be a sensible thing to do. This is an important reason to provide them with clear guidance.
- The *ex situ* component is missing in many IUCN conservation planning exercises.
- The *ex situ* community is also failing on the contents of these guidelines (keep all of the critically endangered species in captivity).
- The current guidelines are not being implemented (important consideration for the implementation phase).

- Some groups have found their own ways to solve the gap that exists because of the lack of clarity in the current guidelines.
- The current guidelines are neither guidelines nor a policy.
- The group felt that we need a more concrete tool to give guidance.
- A decision tree should preferably be part of the new draft.

Revising the Guidelines

After some discussion it was decided that we need all of the following:

- A vision for intensively managed populations (IMPs)
- A policy statement for taking animals from the wild
- A technical decision-making tool
- A description of *ex situ* roles benefitting conservation to be inserted in SSC Strategic Planning for Species handbook

Another working group was formed to develop a vision for IMPs, leaving the discussion of a policy statement and decision-making tool to this group. Two possible ways to proceed were suggested to produce a more concrete tool:

1. Develop a decision tool (like the Amphibian Ark conservation planning tool) or a decision tree or similar system that gives the user a concrete 'fixed' answer.

OR

2. Develop a decision-making process that gives the user:
 - The steps in the decision-making process, in the right order;
 - The factors that should be considered in each step; but
 - Does not automatically lead to one particular answer.

The Amphibian Ark has developed a useful tool already – the AArk Conservation Needs Assessment Tool – which includes conservation action types/roles, feasibility, and some triggers for establishing *ex situ* populations. The first part of this tool is based on the *in situ* situation and gives guidance on if and what conservation action (not only *ex situ* actions) is needed, including prioritization. The second part targets the feasibility of any *ex situ* component (facilities, expertise, etc). The AArk tool is designed to be cryptic to deal with bias from users who may be invested in a particular outcome.

The working group decided on the following workflow:

Short-Term (to be started during this workshop): Develop a decision-making process. Ensure that the steps for the decision-making process, as well as the factors to be considered at each step, are identified and integrated into a rewritten version of the IUCN existing guidelines.

Medium-Term: Revised text delivered to IUCN for review and endorsement.

Long-Term: Based on the revised guidelines (developed from this working group), build a tool or suite of decision-making tools that give more “fixed” answers.

Steps in the Decision-Making Process

The following steps were recommended to be followed to determine whether it is desirable to take individuals from the wild to support species conservation:

1. Gather the relevant information about the species in the wild (and in captivity) as part of a Status Review, including a threat analysis;
2. Define which potential role(s) that an *ex situ* population might contribute to the conservation of the taxon, in order to address specific status issues and threats identified under Step 1;
3. Determine what forms(s) the *ex situ* population would need to take in order to fulfill those roles;
4. Define what it would take to set up *ex situ* populations in those forms (individuals, facilities, husbandry expertise, resources, etc.) and consider feasibility, risks and likelihood of success; and
5. Make a decision that is informed (i.e. uses the information gathered above) and transparent (i.e. demonstrates how and why the decision was taken).

The guidelines should outline specific issues that should be considered at each stage – for example, which aspects of the status review and threat analysis are particularly relevant, what are the main different kinds of roles that *ex situ* populations play, what are the main forms of *ex situ* populations, what issues should be considered in a feasibility and risk analysis, and some examples of how Steps 1-4 have been used to come to decisions.

The group discussion identified the following issues that should be taken into account when revising the guidelines:

- There are some very strong sections in the existing guidelines (such as relating to the Convention on Biological Diversity, language used that is equally applicable to all taxa, etc.) that should be kept in any revised guidelines. There is, however, scope for changing words to alter emphasis, philosophy, etc.
- It was suggested to rename the document as the current name is not appropriate; it is about more than *ex situ* populations. We need to remember that we are talking about a continuum of management, rather than thinking of *ex situ* vs *in situ* as two separate categories vs ends of the spectrum; therefore, perhaps we should not use the term '*ex situ*.'
- There are other significant initiatives underway within the SSC that are likely to relate to this document and that we will need to take into account (e.g. revision of reintroduction guidelines).
- It may be desirable to include some recommendations (as in the Reintroduction Guidelines) on considerations once individuals have been removed from the wild (i.e. monitoring against measurable objectives, etc.)
- IUCN guidelines do not have any power and are not necessarily recognized by authorities, who can choose to ignore the guidelines. It is important that the revised guidelines are accepted by the relevant authorities (to give it some teeth).
- The drafting process will be carried out under the auspices of the Conservation Breeding Specialist Group (CBSG) and with wide consultation with representatives from various taxon based SGs (to make sure the guidelines can apply to all major taxa), from the Reintroduction SG, the Invasive Species SG and the Species Conservation Planning Task Force, from different *ex situ* organizations/initiatives, etc. We will have to take into account the CBD, as was the case the current guidelines.
- Keep in mind that the revised guidelines and/or tools should be in line with the rest of the IUCN terminology and other documents.

The working group then discussed each of the steps of the suggested process to brainstorm factors or issues that should be considered during each step.

Status Review (Step 1)

What factors do you want to consider about the biology and status of the species and the threats to its viability and survival? It was recognized that it is helpful to 'think like a population modeler' to generate a list of factors that affect the viability, persistence and conservation of a species. Identified factors were:

- Risk of extinction (and the ability to reduce this risk)
- Population growth rate/trend (current and anticipated)
- Ability to mitigate the threats (over time)
- Ability to withstand loss of individuals (temporary or sustained)
- Population size and degree of fragmentation
- Size of habitat (carrying capacity) and trend
- Sex/age structure of the population
- Effective population size (N_e)
- Natural threats
- Catastrophic risks
- Anthropogenic threats (e.g., poaching, over-collection, road mortality)
- Human-animal conflicts
- Cultural significance
- Genetic uniqueness
- Genetic status
- Life history characteristics
- Breeding strategy (difficult ones)
- Migratory species
- Lack of knowledge, data deficient
- Degree of confidence in data on biology, status and threats

The definition of population should not influence the structure of the tool. The tool needs to work on different levels (leopards in general, leopards in South Africa, etc.). Replace 'species' with 'taxon'.

This list includes factors that are included in the Amphibian Ark tool, Red List assessment and SCS Handbook. There are similar lists for plants, but they were not available to the working group, but this needs to be checked later.

Potential Roles for *Ex Situ* (Step 2)

Potential roles (purpose/function) of a population for contributing to conservation include:

- Insurance population (bringing a species in captivity to prevent extinction), and as a potential source population for reintroduction
- Temporary rescue from imminent threat (e.g., hurricanes, disease). Can be local populations.
- Source for ecological or habitat restoration
- Temporary rescue (take into captivity) to reduce mortality due specific life stage (e.g., head start) (e.g., harvest and incubate turtle eggs, and release after hatching)
- Source for demographic supplementation
- Source for genetic supplementation
- Research that will benefit conservation of wild populations (e.g., methods, life history information)
- Research in husbandry in surrogate species
- Proactive husbandry research for specific species before they become threatened (taxonomic uniqueness, cultural reasons, etc.)
- Training – (possible) surrogate animals/populations (to practice trapping, microchipping, etc.).
- Production for human 'consumption' to decrease harvesting of wild populations (controversial, sometimes ineffective or even counterproductive)
- Ambassadors for fundraising for conservation activities (may not be endangered species)
- Public awareness and change in human behavior

A general remark is to check the wording. As decided earlier it is not only about animals it is also about plants, corals, etc. Related to this we have to make sure that the terminology is consistent.

There was a general feeling that populations should not be kept indefinitely in captivity only as part of a conservation strategy.

Program Characteristics (Step 3)

Examples of dimensions of *ex situ* programs are:

- Geographic/location scale (in range vs outside, centralized vs multi-facility)
- Time scale (may be better to work in generations instead of years)
- Off- and/or on-exhibit
- Breeding vs non breeding populations
- Live individuals vs tissues/gametes
- Preservation of "founders" vs reproduction/multiple generations
- Archive of genetic time steps

It is possible to develop a matrix consisting of roles vs program characteristics such as scale, time, etc., to indicate the factors that need to be considered or conditions that need to be met to fulfill each role. There was discussion, however, about how detailed the guidelines should be. On the other hand, people need to be aware of all of these aspects and have to consider them before they can decide if a potential *ex situ* population can fulfill a certain role.

The group decided that rather than produce a matrix for the guidelines, it would be more appropriate and useful to develop a list of relevant program characteristics. The matrix can be part of the decision-making tool.

List of characteristics:

- Whole organism vs parts
- Generations in captivity (one or multiple generations)
- Timescale (in years)
- Adaptation to captivity
- Intensity of genetic management
- Human proximity (losing wildness)

- Visibility for public
- Biosecurity issues
- Artificial selection/adaptation to captivity is an issue (genetic, phenotypic, behavioral adaptation)
- In range state vs outside of range
- Number of facilities
- Population size

Feasibility / Risk Assessment (Step 4)

It is not sufficient to know the potential value of an *ex situ* program designed to meet a specific conservation role – it is also critical to evaluate the feasibility of successfully managing such a program, the costs and resources needed, the likelihood of success, and the risks (including risks to the species in the wild, and to other conservation activities). Some of the factors to be considered include.

- Risk analysis (invasiveness, institutional infrastructural risk, facilities)
- Benefits/costs analysis (bad or good PR, taking place for other species, etc.)
- Disease risk (biosecurity)
- Resources
- Costs
- Husbandry expertise
- Probability of reaching goal/likelihood of success
- Risk if breeding is done incorrectly (e.g., decisions were based on faulty data)
- Welfare considerations
- Assessment of likely impact on the remaining wild population of establishing, or not establishing, an *ex situ* population (accommodating for situations where all remaining wild individuals may have to be removed because of very high probability of extinction that cannot be mitigated in the wild in time); see threat analysis and ability of wild population to withstand loss of individuals in Step 1.

Evaluation (Step 5)

It would be useful to have discussions about the philosophy or any guiding principles that users can use to assimilate the information from Steps 1- 4 to make a recommendation about *ex situ* management as part of an overall species conservation strategy. This could be presented graphically if this is thought to be useful – for example, with a graph that depicts conservation benefits of *ex situ* (based on Steps 1 & 2) versus likelihood of success (Step 4 partly depending on Step 3), and a line/curve/shading that illustrates the suggested relationship between these two axes in recommending *ex situ* management. Examples of such graphs are given below – on which shading or lines could be placed to indicate the basic philosophy. For example, in the line graph, the blue line indicates an equal, linear relationship between benefit and feasibility; the red line weighs conservation benefit more highly (i.e., *ex situ* management is recommended even if feasibility is somewhat low as long as potential benefit is sufficiently high); and the green line suggests the opposite philosophy (i.e., *ex situ* management is not recommended unless feasibility is at least moderately high). The matrix on the right compares value vs effort with a preference for low effort and high value. Other relationships or guiding principles might also be considered.

Next Steps

The desired end result of the revision of these guidelines is a good, explicit technical IUCN-approved decision process (to be decided later how explicit). To get there, we need consultation with and input from other taxa experts (e.g., marine mammals, invertebrates) and discipline experts (reintroduction, invasive species, etc.).

After consultation it was decided to prepare a proposal for revision of the current IUCN guidelines that can be discussed by the IUCN/SSC Steering Committee during their meeting in December. The Steering Committee then can give any direction to the discussion and decide if they agree with revising the current guidelines according the form and scope proposed. If the Steering Committee agrees, a draft of the revised guidelines can be prepared for further discussion during the midyear meeting in 2011.

As the Reintroduction Guidelines also are being revised at this time, it will be good to stay abreast of this process to make sure that both guidelines are in line with each other. The reintroduction guidelines can also function as example for the level of detail.

To make sure that the bio banking concept will be covered it is suggested to involve 'Catherine Cannon' as she is working on a similar process for bio banking (action working group).

Addendum: At its December 2010 meeting, the SSC Steering Committee gave approval for CBSG and its colleagues to pursue revision of the IUCN guidelines for review and approval by the SSC and its subcommittees.

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